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Human Development among Primitive Tribes in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The present paper attempts to extend the conceptual framework of human development developed by United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to household level and probes in to the variations in the levels of development of primitive tribes (PGTs) in Tamil Nadu. It is based on household survey conducted in Nilgiri Districts of Tamil Nadu. The results of the study indicate significant variations in the human development among the primitive tribes in Tamil Nadu. Badaga the non-scheduled primitive tribe was found to be the most advanced among them while the Kurumba was found to be least developed. The process of human development among the primitive tribes engineered by the planning and policy making in the country has been still mediated by the agency of tribe. The historical and geographical factors along with the socio economic and political factors still determine the level of human development. The tribal policy and planning over a half a century could not succeed in addressing these historical and structural forces.

Keywords: *human development, human development index, primitive tribe*

Introduction

Schedule Tribes (STs) are socially excluded section of Indian society, economy and polity over centuries. According to the 2001 Census they are 84.3 million constituting 8.20 per cent of the country's population. The numerically small primitive tribal groups (PTGs)¹ constitute the most isolated among them. They are about 1.32 million population with 1.57 per cent of the total population in the country. The ST population in Tamil Nadu is 6,51,321 and constitutes 1.04 per cent of the population of the state as per the 2001 census. The

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PTGs form 33.46 per cent of the ST population and 0.35 percent of the total population in the state as per the 2001 census. In the state there are 36 STs, of which 6 viz., Toda, Kota, Kurumba, Irula, Paniyan and Kattunayakan are PTGs. The national five-year plans and ongoing tribal sub plan (TSP) approach are focussing on the development of primitive tribal groups (PTGs). In fact the Government of India has conceded that the problem of extinction of primitive tribes is one of the persisting problems of tribals in the tenth plan².

Development and integration of the STs are two inter related goals of the policy of the government in India since independence. The constitution of India prescribes a number of measures for protection and promotion of the rights of tribals. The Nehruvian tribal *panchsheel* as well as the official tribal policy in India have committed to the integration of tribal communities through development. Nine five-year plans have been executed by the successive national governments. A number of welfare and development programmes have been implemented to ameliorate the tribal lot at the central and state levels. Half a century has passed since the dawn of independence in India. However, the question still remains lingering in the minds of policy makers, planners, academics and social workers committed to the tribal uplift is that how far the goal of development has been accomplished in the context of primitive tribes.

There is a copious literature on tribal development based on the studies conducted at different tribal zones of India by government bodies as well as academic institutions. There are number of studies on tribal standard of living which focus on the economic conditions of tribal households in terms of income, expenditure etc (for instance see Ramachandran, 1992; Karuppaiyan, 1990; Manivannan, 1989; Rajarathnam and Guruswami, 1987). There are studies on the specific tribal problems such as indebtedness, land alienation, poverty etc (see Saravanan, 2001; Rao and Baskaradoss, 1989; Roy Burman, 1972). These studies discuss the nature, extent, causes, agency, and consequences of these problems on tribal life. Tribal education is yet another area widely studied (for instance Mittal and Sharma 1998; Naidu and Pradhan 1973). Tribal educational advancement, enrolment, continuity, dropout etc were focused. Tribal health is focused by

much studies (see Basu and Kshatriya, 1994; 1992). Nutritional status, morbidity, adult and child mortality and their socio-economic and cultural correlates were focus of these studies. Most of these micro level studies have not conceived and measured development as multidimensional process (except Karuppaiyan, 1990). Even this exceptional study fails to clearly lay down the dimensions of development, which may be due to the theoretical vacuum. Further there are not many studies on the problem of development of the primitive tribes in India. The present study tries to fill this research gap by way of employing human development perspective, which has widely been recognized as an alternative approach to economic growth (GNP) model.

Ever since the publication of first Human Development Report (HDR 1990), the literature on human development it is ever growing. Apart from the global HDRs (1990-2003), there are regional reports (see Haq, 1992), national reports (see Shariff 2001). In India, there are a number of attempts to analyse human development at disaggregate level such as interstate comparison (see Malgavkar, 1994; Prabhu and Chatterji, 1993; Shiva Kumar, 1991) and inter district comparison (Government of Tamil Nadu, 2002; Geetha Rani, 1999; Vyasulu and Vani, 1997; Prabhu, 1992). The major gap in the literature is that beyond the district level, human development has not been operationalised. The analysis of the development at community and household levels, human development perspective would be fruitful to monitor development and effectiveness of social policy interventions on various sections of population by way of identifying the factors related to it. The present study fills this research gap by way of assessing human development at micro level.

The focus of the present study is to test the hypothesis that household human development attainment differs between the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga and scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula. This hypothesis draws its inspiration from the earlier studies on tribal education (see Singh and Nayak, 1997). Though, rarely we could find such studies on standard of living or health status, the fact that the tribal communities are at different stages of economic development has been well recognised (see for instance Vidyarthi and Rai, 1985, Majumdar and Madan, 1970; Dube, 1969). This hypothesis focuses of on the

difference in the level of household human development attainment between the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga and scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula. This hypothesis has been drawn in the tribal context where the Badagas were the settled agriculturists and were on the top in the local social hierarchy and considered as superior to the Kota, Kurumba and Irula tribes in the past. Further, the Kota had a protest movement for social mobility and against the domination of Badaga (see Mandelbaum, 1972: 300-301, 469-471, 603)³. The interventions to promote education, health and standard of living by the government and NGOs targeted the scheduled primitive tribes. Hence, the results would throw light on the effects of the various interventions on development and integration of scheduled primitive tribes also.

The results of the present will be useful to policy makers as well as grass root level social workers concerned with tribal development. There is an urgent need to understand the levels of human development of primitive tribes as it is accepted as one of the goals of planning in India since the 9th plan. On the basis of the analysis of the household human development the study will suggest some directions for tribal policy making and programming for tribal development focussing the primitive tribes. The grass root voluntary organisations and social workers in the field will be able to design their interventions strategies for human development. The advocacy groups also will be able to find the policies for tribal empowerment.

Methodology

The present study is cross sectional in nature and based on the primary data collected through field survey with structured household interview schedule and the unit of analysis being the household. A structured household interview schedule was employed to collect primary data from the sample households. The schedule included demographic, social, economic and information of each of the households. The schedule was administered through personal interviews with most knowledgeable person of the household chosen. The personal interview ranged between 30 to 45 minutes normally. The fieldwork was conducted during the months of January and February

2003 and the reference period was the agricultural year 2002.

In the present study, a multistage sampling procedure was followed in the selection of the district, block, tribes, hamlets and households, which is described as under. The *first stage* was the selection of district. The primitive tribes in Tamil Nadu include six tribes viz., Kota, Toda, Kurumba, Irulas and Kattunaickans forming 33.46 per cent of the total tribal population in Tamil Nadu. In view of the fact that all the PTGs are living in the Nilgiris the district was chosen for the present micro level study. The *second stage* of sampling was the selection of block. In the Nilgiris district, there are four administrative blocks, viz., Udthagamandalam, Coonoor, Kotagiri and Gudalure. Among these Gudalur and Kotagiri had high concentration of Tribal population (5-10%). In view of the number of the tribes and their concentration the Kotagiri block was chosen. Selection of the tribes forms the *third stage* of sampling. In the Kotagiri block, five primitive tribes are concentrated. In two ways they may be classified. Firstly, the scheduled primitive tribes of Toda, Kota, Kurumba and Irula and the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga. Secondly these tribes may be classified as the massif tribes and sub-tropical tribes on the basis of their location on the Nilgiris Mountains. The massif tribes of the Toda, Badaga and Kota are racially different from the sub-tropical tribes the Kurumba and Irula. The former are fair while the latter are dark in complexion and have racial affinity (see Thurston, 1909). Apart from racial difference the climate soil, rainfall on the massif is favourable economically too. Among the five primitive tribes the non-scheduled tribe Badaga and scheduled tribes of Kota, Kurumba and Irula were chosen. This is mainly because the concentration of Toda is not sufficient for sampling i.e. they live in only one-hamlet (Mund) constituting only 20 households. As statistical analysis of quantitative data for hypothesis testing warrants large sample, the Toda was excluded from the sample.

Having chosen the tribes, the *next stage* of selection was the choice of hamlets. The choice was made after having discussions with the NGO workers, Government grass root level workers, tribal leaders and making a number of visits to the settlements. One hamlet each to represent each of the four tribes was chosen. It was ensured that the socio economic conditions of the village chosen would reflect

the general conditions of the particular tribe. The *last stage* was the selection of the households. Separate lists of the heads of the households of the four hamlets were prepared in consultation with the key informants of each of the hamlet. From the lists of the four hamlets one half of the households from each of the hamlet, were chosen randomly using lottery method with replacement. The present sample size was arrived at, to ensure large sample in each of the four tribes, as it is needed for analysis of quantitative data for hypothesis testing. Thus the sub sample size arrived at for Badaga, Kota, Kurumba and Irula were 72, 32, 30 and 38 respectively.

Operationalisation of Household Human Development

Conceptually, Household Human Development Index is similar to UNDP's Human Development Index (HDI) and has three components viz., long healthy living, knowledge and resources for decent standard of living but its operationalisation is somewhat different. As measuring life expectancy at household is not possible, health perception index has been used as a proxy measure⁴. A five-point scale of health perception: Very Good, Good, Fair, Poor, and Very Poor was included in the household interview schedule and the same was obtained from the respondent for each member of the household. These five points respectively were given 1,0.75, 0.50, 0.25 and 0 scores so as to converge on the scale of the other three components. To assess the knowledge, a Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI) was constructed⁵. HEAI is a proportion of sum of years of education of all the members of the household to the sum of potential years of education⁶. Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI) has captured the component of resources for living decent standard of life⁷. The HSLI is the weighted composite of Household Per capita Income Index (HPII), and Household Per capita Asset Index (HPAI)⁸. All these component indices range from 0 to 1, similar to UNDP (2003) HDI.

Aggregation and weighting of the components and sub-components is one of the major operational issues. UNDP (1990) equally weights the three components as capability theory, deems that one capability cannot be substituted for the other. Technically it has established with the help of the principal components analysis that the three

components have been highly correlated and with the same level of factor loading. But it assigns one-third weight to gross enrollment (mean years of schooling) and two third weights to adult literacy. Yet, there is no explanation for under weighting of the education of the future generation by the UNDP. It is felt that weighting is all the more necessary in the present context because the scales of the three indices differ. Unlike the UNDP's (1990-2003) HDI, the present HHDI is differentially weighted and the weights were assigned with the help of factor analysis with principal components method. The Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI), Household Health Perception Index (HHPI), and Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI) were factor analysed and the factor score derived from the analysis was transformed into an index ranging from 0 to 1, finding the maximum and the minimum, and considered as the Household Human Development Index (HHDI). The maximum and the minimum for index construction in each of the components were drawn from the sample itself⁹. But, for fixing maximum of the potential years of education, 15 years was fixed as maximum, which is the maximum mean year of education (UNDP, 1993).

The results of factor analysis of the components of standard of living with Principal Components method is presented table 1. Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity revealed the suitability of the sample data. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy was 0.500, which is equal to the required minimum 0.50, and the approximate Chi-square of Bartlett's test of Sphericity (40.98) was found to be significant at 1 per cent level. The sub-components of standard of living converged and formed a single dimension as only one factor was extracted from the analysis of two indices, viz., per capita asset, and per capita income index. Both indices had equal and very high factor loading (0.855). The underlying factor, standard of living accounted 73 per cent of variation of all the sub-components. Since both the indices had equal factor loading, equal weights were assigned and the simple average of both was considered as the Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI).

The Household Health Perception Index (HHPI), Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI) and Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI) were further factor analysed to achieve a

holistic and appropriately weighted measure of household human development (see table 2). The KMO measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity revealed the adequacy and suitability of the data for factor analysis. The KMO (0.55) was greater than 0.5 minimum requirement, while the approximate Chi-square of Bartlett's test of Sphericity (65.73) was significant at 1 per cent level. The PC extracted only one factor, which could be called human development wherein all the components had higher factor loading. Household education attainment index had the greatest factor loading (0.851), closely followed by the household health perception index (0.764) and the household standard of living index (0.604). The underlying factor i.e., Household Human Development explained about 56 per cent of the variation in the variation of all the components, which is large enough to proceed with the analysis further. The weighted factor score derived from PC analysis was transformed into an index ranging from 0 to 1 and that was considered as Household Human Development Index (HHDI). The index was used to analyse inter-tribal variation among the four primitive tribes and test the first hypothesis.

Results and Discussion

Patterns of Inter-Tribal Variation in Human Development

The question here is: how do the households of the four primitive tribes differ in terms of the Human Development and its components viz., health, standard of living and education attainment. To analyse the intertribal variation in human development and its components, one-way analysis of variance (with LSD as post hoc test) was used and the results are presented in table 3.

Long Healthy Living

Long healthy living is the first and foremost component of human development. In the long healthy living attainment, represented by the household health perception index (HHPI) there was significant inter-tribal variation observed. The F ratio of HHPI (18.05) was significant at 1 per cent level.

The households of the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga (0.774) had better healthy living than the scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota (0.637), the Kurumba (0.543), and the Irula

(0.593). The mean differences between the Badaga and the Kota, the Badaga and the Kurumba and the Badaga and the Irula in the household health perception index were significant at 5 per cent level.

Among the scheduled primitive tribes, the Kota households had greater attainment in healthy living as compared to the Kurumba but were at same level with the Irula. The mean difference in HHPI between the Kota and the Kurumba was significant at 5 per cent level, while that of the Kota and the Irula was not significant at 5 per cent level. Further, the households of the Kurumba and the Irula, the sub-tropical tribes, were found to be at the same level of attainment in healthy living. The mean difference in HHPI between the Kurumba and the Irula households was not significant at 5 per cent level.

The better healthy living of the Badaga could be attributed to their better access to nutritious food, better hygienic practices, housing and sanitation on the one hand and their access to health care system on the other. These all are directly related to their economy and culture. The better health of the Kota and the Irula could be attributed to their better access to health care, especially, the Government hospitals and Nilgiri Adivasi Welfare Association (NAWA)'s Medical Services. The Kotas protest movement for social mobility and modernisation played a vital role in doing away with such practices as of eating carrion, would have also played a vital role in improving their life style. The poor health of the Kurumba households is mainly due to their lack of access to nutritious food, prevalence of genetic disorders such as sickle cell anaemia (see Ramasamy *et al*, 1994; Basu, 1994) as well as their location in remote inaccessible forest area. A close observation in the field and interaction with the key informants indicates that the better health status of the Badaga and the poor health status of the Kurumba are closely related to their economic condition. Similar views on the relationship between economic conditions and health among the tribals are widely reported in the literature too (see Zanver *et al.*, 1998; Hiramani, 1997; Gopal, 1996).

Educational Attainment

Educational attainment has been analysed with the help of

Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI), which is a ratio of the sum of actual years of education of the members of the household to the sum of their potential years of education.

Analysis of HEAI with ANOVA also revealed inter-tribal variation among the four primitive tribes. The F ratio for HEAI (27.84) is significant at 1 per cent level. Similar significant inter-tribal variation in education has been reported by earlier studies also (see Singh and Nayak, 1997; Mittal and Sharma, 1998b).

The households of massif tribes of the Badaga (0.585) and the Kota (0.581) had greater education attainment as compared to the sub-tropical tribes of the Kurumba (0.188) and the Irula (0.413). The mean differences in HEAI between the Badaga and the Kota households were not significant at 5 per cent level, while those between the Badaga and the Kurumba, the Badaga and the Irula, the Kota and the Kurumba, and the Kota and the Irula were significant at 5 per cent level. Among the tribes on the massif, the education attainment was at the same level, while among the sub-tropical tribes, the Irula households had greater education attainment as compared to the Kurumba significantly. The mean difference in HEAI between the Irula and the Kurumba was significant at 5 per cent level.

The Badaga households' better education attainment owes much to their economic condition as well as better access to educational institutions. The surprising result is that the Kota households catching up with the Badaga households' education attainment. This is mainly because of their economic advancement as a result of utilisation of government schemes, and access to government schools. The aforesaid the Kotas' protest movement launched by Thiru Sulli of Kollimalai village (see Mandelbaum 1970) would have increased the aspiration for social mobility via education improvement. The relatively better education attainment of the Irula over the Kurumba is due to economic and location factors. The greater size of land holding and proximate location near the centre would have facilitated better education attainment of the former over the latter. One of the key informants reported that the children of his community dropped out of school so as to meet their parents and the parents could not visit the hostel, as they were unable to purchase eatables for their children. Thus poverty and location of hostels near the

headquarters constrain the Kurumba not to cross the primary school.

The field observation and interaction with key informants as well as statistical analysis reveal close association between education attainment and economic condition of the tribal households. Similar results were reported by a number of tribal studies (Mathur, 1994; Kailash, 1993; Rajarathnam and Guruswami, 1987). The importance of geographical location in earlier studies (see Shyamlal, 1987). Role of both these factors was also reported by some studies. (see Mittal and Sharma, 1998c)

Decent Standard of Living

Resources for decent standard of living, is the third component of human development. It was operationalised in the present study as weighted composite of the indices of household per capita income, and household per capita household assets.

In all these components of decent standard of living, significant inter-tribal variation among the four primitive tribes was observed. The F ratio for HSLI by tribe 10.5 is significant at 5 per cent level. Likewise, the F ratio HPAI (5.77) is also significant at 1 per cent level, while that of HPII (3.28) is significant at 5 per cent level.

The households of non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga (0.073) had greater per capita income index as compared to the sub-tropical scheduled primitive tribes of the Irula (0.027) and the Kurumba (0.022), which were on par with the Kota (0.069) households. But among the scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula, there was no significant difference in household per capita income index. The paired mean differences in household per capita income index between the Badaga and the Kota, the Kota and the Irula, the Kota and the Kurumba, the Kurumba and the Irula were not significant at 5 per cent level.

The households of the non-scheduled primitive tribe, the Badaga (0.081), had significantly greater per capita assets when compared to the scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota (0.04), the Irula (0.024), and the Kurumba (0.013). The LSD indicates that the mean differences in HPAI between the Badaga and the Kota, the Badaga and the Kurumba and the Badaga and the Irula are significant at 5 per cent level. But among the households of these scheduled

primitive tribes, there was no significant difference in this component of standard of living. The LSD indicated that the paired mean differences in HPAI between the Kota and the Irula, the Kota and the Kurumba and the Kurumba and the Irula were not significant at 5 per cent level.

When both these two indices were aggregated and the composite index of household standard of living index was analysed, the pattern of inter-tribal variation in standard of living was found to be similar to that of household per capita income. The households of the tribes on the massif, the Badaga (0.08) and the Kota (0.05), had similar level of standard of living. The mean differences between them in HSLI were not significant at 5 per cent level. But the households of the Badaga had better standard of living as compared to the sub-tropical scheduled primitive tribes of the Kurumba and the Irula. The mean differences in HSLI between the Badaga and the Kurumba as well as the Badaga and the Irula were significant at 5 per cent level. Among the scheduled primitive tribes, the standard of living of households of the Kota (0.05), the Kurumba (0.02) and the Irula (0.03), the mean differences between the Kota and the Kurumba, the Kota and the Irula as well as the Kurumba and the Irula in HSLI were significant at 5 per cent level. The Kota households had better standard of living as compared to the sub-tropical primitive tribes the Irula and the Kurumba. Among the sub-tropical tribes the former had better standard of living as compared to the latter.

The observations of the average index values of the four tribes indicate that they were mostly poor in terms of standard of living. The relative better standard of living of the massif tribes of the Badaga and the Kota on the one hand and poorest situation of the Kurumba and the Irula need to be discussed. The better situation of the Badaga and the Kota is mainly due to their settled nature of agriculture and greater size of land holding. The Badaga households had access to better technology (being the first settled agriculturists of Nilgiris), and innovators in technology adoption, and so commercialisation of agriculture with plantation crops resulted in the improvement of their standard of living. The Kota were late in adopting technology but the social mobility and reform movement under the leadership of Thiru Sulli (see Mandelbaum 1970) has

improved their condition and increased their economic aspiration. They have been utilizing the benefits of policy of protective discrimination (both government education and employment). Thus policy of protective discrimination was also favourable to the Kota. The lower standard of living of the Kurumba and the Irula is mainly due the small size of land holding of the former and lack of irrigation facilities to the latter. The rainfall as well as fertility would have worked in favour of the massif tribes and against the sub-tropical tribes. Unfortunately the policy interventions have not taken into account the consideration of these factors and break them in favour of the sub-tropical tribes.

The low level of standard of living of the four primitive tribes was mainly due to the reduction in the price of green tea in the Nilgiris in the Nineties after the new economic policy was implemented in India. This adversely affected the income of marginal and small tea cultivators as well as labourers of the Badaga, the Kota and the Kurumba. The key informants have reported that the members of these tribes were forced to sell their movable and immovable properties so as to meet their consumption needs.

Household Human Development

Aggregating the indices of the three components in Household Human Development Index (HHDI) analyses of inter-tribal variation and levels of human development across the four selected primitive tribes of Tamil Nadu were attempted. Here, an attempt has been made to verify the first hypothesis of the present study that the household human development varies between the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga and the scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula. The testing of hypothesis has been accomplished with the help of one-way analysis of variance and comparison of Least Square Difference (LSD).

The analysis of human development reveals the significant inter-tribal variation across the four primitive tribes of the Badaga, the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula. The F ratio of HHDI (31.93) was significant at 1 per cent level. The households of non-scheduled primitive tribe the Badaga (0.486) had greater human development attainment as compared to the scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota (0.408), the Irula (0.305) and the Kurumba (0.197) significantly.

The LSD comparisons indicate that the mean differences between the Badaga and the Kota, the Badaga and the Irula, the Badaga and the Kurumba were significant at 5 per cent level. The non-scheduled primitive tribe the Badaga households had greatest human development attainment significant among all the tribes. Hence, the first hypothesis that the household human development differs between the non-scheduled primitive tribe of the Badaga and scheduled primitive tribes of the Kota, the Kurumba and the Irula has been validated.

Among these scheduled primitive tribes, the Kota (0.408) households had greater human development attainment as compared to the sub-tropical tribes of the Irula (0.305) and the Kurumba (0.197) significantly. The mean differences in HHDI between the Kota and the Irula as well as between the Kota and the Kurumba were significant at 5 per cent level. Between the two sub-tropical tribes, the Kurumba (0.197) and the Irula (0.305), the latter had greater household human development attainment as compared to the former significantly. The mean difference in HHDI between the Kurumba and the Irula households was significant at 5 per cent level.

The household human development attainments of all the four tribes were found to be not satisfactory by their own standards. The majority of the most advanced tribe (the Badaga) seems to have not even crossed the half way stage. The most backward tribe, the Kurumba suffers mostly due to deprivation in all the components of human development viz., health, education and standard of living. The observations also indicate the interrelatedness of the three components. The geographical location, access to land, irrigation, access to social services (education and health), access to employment of all have been found to play a vital role in affecting human development at household level. These factors work through the agency of tribe as each tribe differs in these terms. The process of globalisation and privatisation implemented ever since 1990 has been adversely impacting on the human development attainment in all its components. It has reportedly affected the standard of living of all the primitive tribes by reducing the prices of green tea, which is the major crop in the Nilgiris. It had reduced the quality of health care in the public hospitals by reducing the availability of medicine

and postponing the appointment of personnel in the public hospitals. The educational institutions of primitive tribes are being adversely affected by the new economic policy. The postponement of appointment of teachers in the government schools from which the tribals benefit has affected the quality of education provided to them.

The inter-tribal variation in human development could be attributed mainly to the interrelated factors viz., geographical location, access to land, fertility and irrigation of land, access to social services and employment mediated by the factor of tribe. The unfortunate situation is that transcending these factors the policy interventions of public action could not benefit the poorest and the weakest sub-tropical tribes and enhance human development. The factors and processes, endogenous to the tribes such as aspiration for development and social mobility also have played a vital role in uplifting the Badaga and the Kota. The location factor constrains the emergence of such movements in the most deprived sub-tropical tribes of the Kurumba and the Irula. It is also unfortunate to note the forces of globalisation and privatisation threaten even such low level of human development attainment. The significant portion of households in the Badaga and the Kota at low level of human development could be attributed to the effect of globalisation forces, while the much greater portion of households among the sub-tropical tribals would also have met such fate.

Conclusions

In the context of primitive tribes of Tamil Nadu, it can be concluded that the level of human development attained is significant though a significant and sizeable number of tribal households were left out. The households of non-scheduled tribe of Badaga the first settled agriculturists in the Nilgiris achieved greater human development among the primitive tribes of the Nilgiris in spite of being excluded from ST list in the post independence. The scheduled primitive tribes of Kota, Irula and Kurumba are still lagging behind the non-scheduled tribe of Badaga the first settled agriculturists in the Nilgiris in spite of being the target of governmental intervention over half a century. Among the scheduled primitive tribes the level of human development is uneven and the sub tropical tribes of Kurumba and Irula are struggling for survival while the level of human development

of the scheduled primitive tribe Kotas is closer to the Badagas. The Kurumba tribe (the sorcerers and hunters) is the least developed among all the PGTs. We argue that access to land and better agricultural technology, favourable agro climatic condition and commercialisation of agriculture, utilisation of government policies and programmes and motivation and aspiration for development generated by protest movement for social mobility constituted the major factors responsible for uneven human development in the Nilgiris. The effects these inter related factors have been mediated by the agency of tribe. Unfortunately, the government policies and programmes failed to address the special needs of the weakest among the primitive tribes.

Suggestions for Policy

The following suggestions were made to accelerate human development and central inclusion of the specific tribes of the Nilgiris.

- (a) The Kurumba tribe, whose households suffer at low level of human development and marginality stage of inclusion, need immediate attention of the government and voluntary sector. Because of the meagre size of land holding they suffer from low income, ill health and illiteracy. The Kurumba tribe needs preferential treatment in educational institutions as well as employment. Ongoing programmes for development of micro enterprises have to be strengthened and focussed on the Kurumba tribes and sustainable income and employment be generated. The involvement of committed NGOs in this endeavour would ensure efficient implementation.
- (b) The Irula is found to be the second most deprived tribe in the Nilgiris. Its major livelihood problem is that of lack of irrigation. Though they are in possession of sizable amount of land, they were found to cultivate a meagre portion of their land due to this problem. Hence, it is suggested to develop an irrigation project connecting the Kallar River through a pipeline and lifting of water through pump set. Subsidized drip irrigation system may also be installed in each of the farm for efficient utilisation of available water. This would increase the area of cropping as well as production, productivity, strengthen the livelihood base, household income and thereby standard of

living and human development of the Irula tribe.

- (c) The problem that daunts the Kota is that of educated unemployment among the youth. Training of the youth in arts and crafts where they have traditional skills on the one hand employment of already trained youth in suitable venture is suggested.

Notes

1. Thurston used the concept of primitive tribes in the context of the Nilgiris as early as 1909. He calls the tribes of the Nilgiris Badaga, Toda, Kota, Kurumba etc. as more or less Hinduised Primitive Tribes. This concept is applied by government of India in its tribal development programmes too and integrated tribal development programme the numerically small primitive tribes are covered by primitive tribal group projects. The Government of India has identified 75 Primitive Tribal Groups (PTGs) with an estimated total population of 1.32 million in 1991, spread over 15 States/Union Territories based on a four-point criteria viz. smallness in size and diminishing in number; backwardness and isolation; use of pre agricultural technology; and very low literacy. According to Government of India (2000) there is a marked difference between the relatively advanced tribal groups and the PTGs. Accordingly the PGTS are subjected to extreme backwardness, when compared to the other tribals as they live in the most interior and inaccessible forests. It also observes that a decline in their sustenance base and the resultant food insecurity, malnutrition and ill-health force them to live in the most fragile living conditions and some of them are even under the threat of getting extinct.
2. In the tenth plan document the Government of India pointed out certain unresolved issues and persisting problems with regard to tribal population of the country, which warrant immediate attention of state and non-state actors. The unresolved issues in tribal development planning according to Government of India (1992) are displacement of tribals, tribal land alienation, indebtedness, shifting cultivation, and deprivation of forest rights while the persisting problems are low literacy and high drop-out rates, inadequate and inaccessible health services, nutritional deficiencies and diseases, lack of adequate irrigation facilities, extreme/abject poverty, endangering of intellectual rights, crimes/atrocities against STs, neglect of forest villages, extinction of primitive tribal groups,

ineffective implementation of PESA, 1996, and routinised mechanism of TSP.

3. Mandelbaum during his fieldwork in the Nilgiris with the Kotas observed over a number of years a mobility contest waged by them vigorously by one man Thiru. Sulli. Mandelbaum (1972:469) “For decades he had to fight a running two-front battle, with the opponents of Kota ambitions and with his opponents among the Kotas. He eventually won on both fronts; his long, tenacious fight certainly affected the status of Kotas during his life and has probably had long-run effects as well”
4. Theoretically, Sen’s capability perspective prefers objective indicators over subjective ones but due to non-availability of such ones subjective indicator has been adopted.
5. The UNDP’s education attainment, which is the composite of the ratio of adult literacy and gross enrollment, could not be computed at household level because the latter ratio needs sufficiently larger population. The present HEAI is more comprehensive than UNDPs (1993) EAI as it takes into actual years of education rather than the binary of literate or illiterate. It captures the disparity in education more accurately than the latter.
6. $HEAI = \frac{\sum A_{ij}}{\sum P_{ij}}$ where A is actual year of education of a member of the household and P is potential year of education a member of the household.
7. At household level, the per capita income alone does not capture the resource base. The inclusion of assets would reveal the capability more comprehensively.
8. The component indices HSLI such as HPII, HPEI, and HPAI were constructed using the following formula used by UNDP to convert the actual values of per capita income, adult literacy life expectancy etc., into indices.
$$\frac{\text{Actual}_{ij} - \text{Minimum}_{ij}}{\text{Maximum}_{ij} - \text{Minimum}_{ij}}$$
9. Goal Posts of UNDP for the other indicators are not available and no standard national or international goals posts on these indicators are available.

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Annexure-I

Table 1: Factor Matrix of Components of Standard of Living

Sl.No	Components	Factor Loading	Communalities (h ²)
1.	Percapita Income Index	0.855	0.73
2.	Percapita Asset Index	0.855	0.73
3.	Eigen Value	1.463	
4.	% of Variance	73.172	
5.	Cumulative %	73.172	

6.	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.500	
	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
	Approx. Chi-Square	40.982**	
	Df	1	
	Sig.	0.00	

Source : Computed **Sugnificant at 1 per cent level

Table 2: Factor Matrix of Components of Human Development

Sl.No	Components	Factor Loading	Communalities (h2)
1.	Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI)	0.604	0.365
2.	Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI)	0.851	0.724
3.	Household Health Perception Index (HHPI)	0.764	0.584
4.	Eigen Value	1.674	0.604
5.	% of Variance	55.791	0.851
6.	Cumulative %	55.791	0.764
7.	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.550	
	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
	Approx. Chi-Square	65.73	

	Df	3	
	Sig.	00.00	

Source: Computed

**Table 3 : Inter tribal Variation in Human Development:
One Way ANOVA**

Sl. No.	Component	Tribe				F
		Bada-ga	Kota	Kuru-mba	Irula	
I	Household Health Perception Index (HHPI)	0.774	0.637 ^a	0.543 ^b	0.593 ^{ab}	18.05 ^{**}
II	Household Education Attainment Index (HEAI)	0.585 ^a	0.581 ^a	0.188	0.413	27.84 ^{**}
III	Household Standard of Living Index (HSLI)	0.08 ^a	0.05 ^{ab}	0.02 ^b	0.03 ^b	10.50 ^{**}
	Household Per capita Income Index	0.073 ^a	0.069 ^{ab}	0.022 ^b	0.027 ^b	3.28 [*]
	Household Per capita Asset Index	0.081	0.040 ^a	0.013 ^a	0.024 ^a	5.77 ^{**}
	Household Human Development Index (HHDI)	0.486	0.408	0.197	0.305	31.93 ^{**}

Source: Source: Computed * Significant at 5 per cent level
** Significant at 10 per cent level